

ISic3184

I.Sicily inscription 3184

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Vigna Cassia

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI329578

1. ἐνθάδε κῆτε

2. Βικτωρῖνος.

3.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645514

PHI 329578

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 04.0010

Orsi, P. 1923. Manipulus epigraphicus christianus memoriae aeternae I.B. de Rossi dicatus. Contributi alla Siracusa sotterranea. *Atti della Pontificia Accademia Romana di Archeologia. Memorie*. 1: 113-122. At no.9

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